

DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY BUSINESS

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Shadieva Gulnora Mardieva

Professor of the Department of Real Economy of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Kuvandikov Shuhrat Oblokulovich

Professor of the Department of Real Economy of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Abstract: *The article examines the issues of increasing the role of the family entrepreneurship in the field of services. It develops a ranking of regions based on statistical indicators that reflect the development of the family entrepreneurship. According to the results of the rating, the development of family entrepreneurship in the service sector in the regions is classified. Scientific and practical recommendations on increasing the role of the family entrepreneurship in the socio-economic development of the regions of Uzbekistan are proposed.*

Key words: *sphere of service, family entrepreneurship, development of regions, level of development of family entrepreneurship, index of development of family entrepreneurship, category of regions, rating of regions.*

Introduction

It is also important to take into account the impact of a family entrepreneurship in assessing the socio-economic development of the regions. Assessing the development of family entrepreneurship is an important tool for the socio-economic development of the regions and plays a special role in ensuring social stability. In this regard, the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 set the task of comprehensive and balanced socio-economic development of regions, districts, and cities[1]. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 1, 2020, No PP-4702 "On the introduction of a rating system of socio-economic development of the regions" aimed at ensuring the implementation of the tasks set out in this concept. The document states that there is no comprehensive assessment mechanism that allows indepth analysis of the current state of socio-economic development of the regions. Therefore, the

goal is to develop a methodology for a comprehensive assessment of the role of a family entrepreneurship in the socio-economic development of the regions. To achieve this goal, you must:

- to analyze the existing methods for assessing the role of family entrepreneurship;
- to develop a methodology for assessing the role of family entrepreneurship at the regional level;
- to test the developed assessment methodology.

Fundamental issues of family business development have been studied by many foreign scholars. Among them are R. C. Anderson, D. M. Reeb, G. A. Tarnowski, D. Prajogo, A. Sohal, T. Beehr, J. A. Drexler, S Faulkner, C. M Daily, M. J. Dollinger and other scholars on the nature of family entrepreneurship and its differences from non-family businesses, Gallo, Miguel Angel, and Jannicke Sveen discuss the role of a family business in economic and industrial development, as well as internationalization issues, CA Romano, G.A. Scholars such as Tarnowski, K.H. Smyrnios, Blanco-Mazagatos V, de Quevedo-Puente E, L.A. Castrillo, have studied the capital structure of a family business, its financial resources, and the factors that affect business costs and financial decisions[8;36], L.M Kelly and Kets de Vries[21;22], issues of strategic planning in the family business, M. Duh, J. Belak, B.Milfelner, W. G. Jr. Dyer, M. C.Vallejo [9;17] characteristics of cultural and ethnic values in the family business, Russian scientists such as A.A. Zhuk, K.M.Potiy, A. Volkov, S. O. Kalendjyan, E.V.Korchagina, V.A. Korolev, and A. Chernitsky [9;13;19;23;24;25], studied the socio-economic nature, types, classification, and theoretical conceptual basis of the family business and the problems of its development. However, these studies have not explored the role of the family business in regional development or service sector development.

A number of problems and factors of the socio-economic development of the regions have been studied. These studied problems can be divided into groups in the following areas:

- Assessment of opportunities for self-development of regions, as well as issues of ensuring integrated sustainable socio-economic development [14;26;27;33];
 - Problems of innovative development of regions [3;18;34];
 - Assessment of the role of small business in the development of regions and their development on the basis of an integrated index, as well as rating indicators, etc[19;20;28;29;31;32;35;36].

It is clear from these studies that there is no single approach to regional development. Research in this area is aimed at addressing various aspects of regional development. However, these approaches do not take into account the role of the family business. Therefore, the issues of integrated use of the above research results in practice remain unclear.

This article develops a methodological approach to assessing the role of the family business in the development of the service sector. Because the prospects of the Uzbek economy in many respects depend on the development of the family business. In this regard, this study is a special method of research in the field of services and plays an important role in the development of effective measures for the development of family business in this area.

Methods

In this study, a mixture of quantitative and qualitative methods was used. This methodology provided the right methodological direction in data collection and analysis, as well as in identifying ways to solve problems. Therefore, a methodological map classification for determining the role of family entrepreneurship in the service sector was developed

The data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan were used in this study. Based on the collected statistics, a system of indicators to assess the role and impact of the family business in the national economy and their calculation formulas were developed (Table 2). This methodology allowed to assess the importance of family businesses for the economy of Uzbekistan.

Table 1. Indicators for assessing the role of family business in the service sector

Indicators	Calculation formula
Number of FB in the field of services operating in the region (units)	-
Number of FB in the field of services per 100 families in the region, (units)	$\frac{\text{FB in the field of services}}{\text{Number of families}} \times 100$
The share of FB in the field of services in the number of Family Businesses operating in the region, (%)	$\frac{\text{FB in the field of services}}{\text{Total number of FB in the region}} \times 100$

Source: developed by authors

The rating of the regions was assessed on a 100-point scale. At the same time, the highest score on the 1st criterion - 34 points, the highest score on the 2nd criterion - 33, 3 points - the highest score on the criterion - 33 points. The rest were rated accordingly to the highest score on the index. On this basis, the rating of the regions was conditionally classified as high (86-100 points) - "green", medium (71-85 points) - "yellow", and low (55-70 points) - "red". A high score on Criterion 3 plays a decisive role when the total score of the regions is the same. Table 5-7 data were used.

This rating was based on the calculation of the integral index "Development of family entrepreneurship in the service sector", which is a set of various indicators that record the actual state of certain aspects of the development of the region. Sources of information for compiling the rating: State Committee on Statistics, Central Bank and the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan, websites of regional authorities, and other open sources. When compiling the rating, the set of indicators used was optimized and the method for calculating the integral index was improved.

Results

There are differences in the development of family business in the field of services in the Samarkand region. By regions, the highest rating score in the index "The role of a family business in the development of services" was recorded in Samarkand (100), Payarik (91), Samarkand (90), Jambay (89), Taylak (89) and Pstdargom districts. Ishtikhan (85), Narpay (83), Kattakurgan (82), Koshrabat (81), Aqdarya (79), Bulungur (78), Urgut (77) districts and Kattakurgan city (73) corresponded to the average rating. The lowest rating scores were recorded in Pakhtachi (69) and Nurabad (67) districts (Table 3).

It was found that their demographic indicators do not have a strong impact on the ranking of regions that rank high on this index. Accordingly, the population of Jambay district (170 thousand) took 4th place with 89 points, although lower than the regional average (240 thousand). A reverse trend was also observed on the same indicator. At the same time, Urgut district ranks 2nd in the region in terms of population (501 thousand) but ranks 13th in this ranking with 77 points (Table 3). However, the city of Samarkand is an exception. Because the city of Samarkand is the administrative center of the region and one of the largest cities in the country in terms of population and territory. Based on this, it can be said that the population of the regions is not an important factor in the development of family business in the service sector.

The scores of this index on the criterion "the number of family businesses per 100 families" played a decisive role in determining the ranking of regions. The scores obtained on this criterion are consistent with their ranking results (Table 3).

The considered 16 subjects of the Samarkand region are proposed to classify them according to the level of development of family business in the service sector. At the same time, based on the rating score of the regions (Table 4), they were classified into high (1-6 places) - "green", medium (7-14 places) - "yellow" and low (15-16 places) - "red" categories .

Analysis

The family business is the oldest and most widespread business institution in the world. At present, special attention is paid to the study of its scientific basis. Therefore, family business plays an important role in the economies of many developed countries around the world. According to the Institute for Family Business (IFB), 87.6% of all businesses in the UK, half of those employed in the private sector (14.2 million), 31% of GDP, 75% of all businesses in Spain, and 65% of GDP in the US 90% of all types of enterprises and 60% of GDP, 18% of total exports in Italy are accounted for by family businesses [42]. Also, according to a survey conducted by PricewaterhouseCoopers (2018), 26% of family businesses worldwide are diversified in several sectors of the economy and markets in different countries[43].

As of January 1, 2020, the number of family businesses operating in the economy of Uzbekistan amounted to 24,137, their share in the total number of operating commercial enterprises was 8.0%, their net income from sales of goods and services amounted to 679,320.3 million soums, their share in family income 55.2%, the number of jobs created due to them is 358.56 thousand [44]. It is obvious that the level of development of family business in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is insufficient. Therefore, the tasks of developing the necessary measures for the further development of family business have been identified [2]. This justifies the need to study family business in all its aspects and to study foreign experience in this area.

Table 3. Results of the rating of Samarkand region on the index "The role of family business in the development of the services sector" (as of January 1, 2020)

	Regions	popul ation	num ber of fami lies	Number of operatin g Family Business es		the share of Family Businesses in the services sector		Number of Family Businesse s per 100 families		Region rating	
				unit y	ba ll	%	ball	unit y	ba ll	Σ ball	pl ac e
	Samarkan d city	543	1086 00	165 8	34	70,5	33	1,5	33	100	1
	Kattakurg an city	89	1780 0	91	22	46,1	22	0,5	29	73	14
	Oqdaryo	157	3140 0	213	25	53,0	24	0,7	30	79	11
	Bulungur	185	3700 0	201	23	55,0	26	0,5	29	78	12
	Jomboy	170	3400 0	318	27	66,0	31	0,9	31	89	4
	Ishtikhon	251	5020 0	465	30	53,0	24	0,9	31	85	7
	Kattakurg an	270	5400 0	267	26	58,0	27	0,5	29	82	9
	Kushrabat	130	2600 0	52	21	69,0	32	0,2	28	81	10
	Narpay	211	4220 0	207	24	62,0	30	0,5	29	83	8
0	Payariq	247	4940 0	533	31	59,0	28	1,0	32	91	2
1	Pastdarg am	350	7000 0	751	33	49,0	23	1,0	32	88	6
2	Paxtachi	143	2860 0	46	20	46,0	21	0,2	28	69	15
3	Samarkan d	249	4980 0	732	32	54,0	25	1,5	33	90	3
4	Nurabad	149	2980 0	45	19	44,0	20	0,2	28	67	16

5	Urgut	501	1002 00	456	29	38,0	19	0,5	29	77	13
6	Tayloq	198	3960 0	412	28	60,0	29	1,0	32	89	5

The analysis of the development of family business in 16 regions of Samarkand showed that the share of operating family businesses in the regions is unevenly distributed. In particular, as of January 1, 2020, the number of registered family businesses in the Samarkand region amounted to 6780, of which 1658 in Samarkand city, 788 in Samarkand district, 786 in Pstdargom district, and 566 in Payarik district, Ishtikhon district - 496 and at least Pakhtachi district - 46, Nurabad district - 51 and Koshrabat district - 53. The highest rate of the share of family businesses not operating in the regions was in Nurabad district - 11.8%, Bulungur district - 7.4%, and Taylak district - 7.2%. During the analyzed period, the largest number of new family enterprises was in Samarkand - 486, and the least - in Nurabad district - 9, the largest number of liquidated family enterprises - in Ishtikhon district - 16, the least - in Jambay and Pakhtachi districts - 1 (table 7).

The share of 6780 family enterprises in the Samarkand region by sectors of the economy is as follows: in agriculture, forestry and fisheries - 8.1% (555), industry - 27.5% (1863), construction - 0.7% (47), services (trade, transportation and storage, accommodation and food services, information and communication, health and social services) - 58% (3917) and in other areas - 5.9% (398). During this period, 94.9% of family businesses in the region, while 5.1% ceased operations for various reasons. If we look at it by industry, in agriculture, forestry and fisheries (95.1% of active, 5.9% of inactive), industry (93.8% of active, 6.2% of inactive), in construction (100% of active, non-operating - no), in all areas of activity in the service sector (95.5% of active, 4.5% of inactive) and in other areas (95.0% of active, 5.0% of inactive). The number of established (2287) and liquidated (88) family enterprises in the region during the analyzed period in agriculture, forestry and fisheries (established - 206, liquidated - 9), industry (established - 525, liquidated - 37), construction (established - 6, liquidated - no), in all areas of activity in the field of services (established - 1470, liquidated - 42) and in other areas (established - 80, liquidated - 5) (Table 7).

Discussions

The current procedure for assessing the rating of regions is based on the criteria developed on the basis of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 1, 2020 No PP-4702 "On the introduction

of a rating system of socio-economic development of regions". Accordingly, the development of the service sector in the regions was assessed on the indicators of "volume of services provided to the population" and "volume of services per capita." Based on this methodology, the results of the rating of the development of the service sector in the regions of Samarkand region confirmed the results of our study. However, the aim of our study was to determine the role of family entrepreneurship in the development of the service sector in the regions. To do this, we determined the share of the family business in all types of activities in the service sector. The analysis showed that the share of family businesses in trade and the provision of accommodation and food services is much higher than in other activities. Therefore, it was concluded that family businesses providing trade, accommodation, and catering services could be a growth point in the development of the service sector. Also, a classification of regions according to the index "The role of the family business in the development of the service sector" was developed and recommendations were made on this basis.

Conclusions

Analysis based on an assessment of the role of the family business in the service sector has shown that economic policy and business conditions have had a strong impact on the development of the regions. This is evidenced by how reforms aimed at improving the business environment in the regions are being implemented. The ranking of the level of development of family business, calculated on the basis of the integral index, allows determining the location of the regions. And on this basis, imbalances in the development of family business in the regions are identified and recommendations for development are given. The methodology developed for assessing the development of the regions was submitted to the Samarkand Regional Department of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction on the basis of indicators reflecting the role of the family business in assessing the socio-economic development of the regions.

It should be noted that, despite numerous scientific studies, it is advisable to expand and develop the theory of regional development in the following areas:

- important socio-economic indicators of socio-economic development of the regions are in need of an additional developmental classification system;

- based on the results of the study, it was concluded that there are still conflicting views in determining the socio-economic nature of regional development;

- the study did not take into account the role and place of the family business in regional development. Therefore, there were difficulties in combining or generalizing the results of research on the development of regions on the basis of synergetic principles.

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